

DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL FACILITATION

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Abstract. *This article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations for developing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation. The study analyzes the process of forming competencies through collaboration between teacher and student, student-centered approaches, support for professional motivation, and the encouragement of independent thinking and creative activity within the framework of pedagogical facilitation. The research substantiates the essential role of the facilitator teacher, pedagogical conditions, interactive teaching methods, and reflective activity in enhancing students' professional competence. Experimental findings demonstrate significant improvements in students' professional knowledge, skills, communicative culture, reflective thinking, and sense of responsibility. The results confirm that the implementation of facilitation technologies in teacher education is an effective approach to strengthening students' professional preparation.*

Keywords: *pedagogical facilitation, professional competence, facilitator teacher, motivation, reflection, collaboration, competence-based approach, professional development.*

Introduction

In the context of rapid advancement and renewal of scientific-technical information worldwide, as well as ongoing socio-economic and scientific-technological transformations, technologies for developing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation are increasingly being integrated into the educational process. In accordance with the resolution of the 36th session of the UNESCO General Conference held in Paris in 2011, various practical initiatives have been implemented to develop facilitation methods through training and seminars, engage students as active participants in case-based learning, problem-solving, and role-play activities, organize discussions and debates, enhance reflection and analytical skills, design personalized learning pathways, support initiative and creativity, and establish psychologically comfortable learning environments to reduce stress and anxiety.

In leading educational and research institutions around the world, scientific-practical studies are being conducted on the development of models for enhancing students' professional competencies through pedagogical facilitation based on cognitive psychology, constructivism, and humanistic pedagogy. These efforts aim to improve students' socio-personal thinking skills, modernize educational processes in accordance with international standards, and enhance the quality and efficiency of teaching. Particular attention is given to determining the role of facilitators in education, implementing personalized learning approaches, ensuring the sustainability of professional competence development, and integrating facilitation with modern technologies.

In recent years in Uzbekistan, significant foundations have been established for integrating artificial intelligence, virtual reality, gamification, and other innovations into pedagogical

facilitation. The use of facilitation methods in the teaching process has been identified as a key factor in ensuring students' personal and professional development, as well as enhancing their moral-ethical competence. In this regard, programs implemented in educational institutions aim to strengthen students' moral resilience and prepare them to find innovative solutions to professional challenges. As a result, opportunities for developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation are expanding.

Research Aim

The aim of the study is to develop recommendations for enhancing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation.

Research Objectives

- To identify the pedagogical opportunities for developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation;
- To select an effective model for professional competence development through pedagogical facilitation and improve its methodological foundations;
- To enhance the processes of developing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation;
- To determine the effectiveness of pedagogical facilitation in fostering students' professional competence.

Research Methods

In the research process, a set of methods was used, including theoretical methods (study and analysis of educational-methodical literature, comparison, analogy), diagnostic methods (survey, testing, observation), prognostic methods (assessment of learning outcomes, expert evaluation, generalization of independent assessments, modeling), pedagogical experimentation, and mathematical-statistical analysis of results.

Research Object

The object of the research is the process of developing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation. The study involved 425 students from Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Gulistan State University, and Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute.

Research Subject

The subject of the research is the forms, methods, and tools for developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation. The purpose of the pedagogical experimental work is to increase the effectiveness of developing students' professional competence on the basis of pedagogical facilitation. The experimental work was carried out in three stages: diagnostic, formative, and final — analyzing the results.

At the diagnostic stage, psychological, pedagogical, and scientific-methodological sources related to developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation were systematically studied. The scientific-theoretical foundations, objectives, and tasks of the research were clarified; the object of research, its indicators, and corresponding criteria were identified. The issue of developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation was analyzed in terms of individual characteristics, and relevant scientific literature and regulatory documents were examined.

During this stage, the content of activities carried out in higher education institutions to develop students' professional competence, their legal-normative basis, and implementation mechanisms were analyzed. Pedagogical methods aimed at enhancing social relations among students were developed. Cooperation mechanisms between higher education institutions, student

involvement in social-active activities, differentiated and individual approaches, and students' participation in scientific, practical, and public initiatives were studied. In addition, the system of organizing students' free time effectively, the cooperation between parents and educational institutions, and innovative forms of collective work were examined. At the diagnostic stage, questionnaire surveys were conducted among teachers and students to identify the level of students' professional competence, existing pedagogical processes, challenges, and barriers. Since the research was carried out at university and inter-faculty levels, the survey questions had an integrative nature. The results of this stage justified the necessity of introducing a pedagogical model aimed at developing students' professional competence. Based on the results of the initial diagnostic monitoring conducted during the first stage, the following conclusions were drawn (the results table is presented below).

Table 1

Criteria	HEIs	Groups	Number of students	High		Medium		Low	
				in number	in %	in number	in %	in number	in %
Axiological	Gulistan State University	Experimental group	68	5	7,4%	13	19,1%	50	73,5%
		Control group	67	6	9,0%	11	16,4%	50	74,6%
	Nizami Tashkent State Pedagogical University	Experimental group	75	7	9,3%	14	18,7%	54	72,0%
		Control group	76	6	7,9%	16	21,1%	54	71,1%
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	Experimental group	70	6	8,6%	15	21,4%	49	70,0%
		Control group	69	5	7,2%	16	23,2%	48	69,6%
	Grand total	Experimental group	213	18	8,5%	42	19,7%	153	71,8%
		Control group	212	17	8,0%	43	20,3%	152	71,7%
Gnoseological	Gulistan State University	Experimental group	68	6	8,8%	14	20,6%	48	70,6%
		Control group	67	6	9,0%	13	19,4%	48	71,6%
	Nizami Tashkent State Pedagogical University	Experimental group	75	7	9,3%	15	20,0%	53	70,7%
		Control group	76	7	9,2%	16	21,1%	53	69,7%
	Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute	Experimental group	70	6	8,6%	15	21,4%	49	70,0%
		Control group	69	6	8,7%	14	20,3%	49	71,0%
	Grand total	Experimental group	213	19	8,9%	44	20,7%	150	70,4%
		Control group	212	19	9,0%	43	20,3%	150	70,8%
Praxeological	Gulistan State University	Experimental group	68	5	7,4%	14	20,6%	49	72,1%

		Control group	67	5	7,5%	13	19,4%	49	73,1 %
	Nizami Tashkent State Pedagogical University	Experimental group	75	6	8,0%	15	20,0%	54	72,0 %
		Control group	76	6	7,9%	16	21,1%	54	71,1 %
	ukhara State Pedagogical Institute	Experimental group	70	6	8,6%	14	20,0%	50	71,4 %
		Control group	69	6	8,7%	14	20,3%	49	71,0 %
	Grand total	Experimental group	213	17	8,0%	43	20,2%	153	71,8 %
		Control group	212	17	8,0%	43	20,3%	152	71,7 %

At the second — formative stage of the experimental research, the process of developing students’ professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation was systematized within the context of in-class and extracurricular activities. For this purpose, independent study modules, methodological recommendations, and instructional materials designed for training sessions were integrated into the educational process and piloted. During this stage, the social-active citizenship model was widely applied and tested in order to develop students’ logical thinking abilities, social activeness, and creative thinking skills within the framework of pedagogical facilitation.

To conduct the educational experiment, a seminar program titled “*Innovative Technologies for Developing Students’ Professional Competence*” was developed for teachers and students. Within the scope of the program, a social brochure titled “*Modern Approaches to Organizing Education*” was created. Throughout the seminar-training sessions, university administrators, teachers, and students were motivated towards professional interaction and prepared for mutual professional communication.

During this stage, a set of socio-psychological and academic case studies was prepared within short-term mobile courses to encourage and sustain the development of teachers’ and students’ professional competence. These cases consisted of questions and tasks aimed at preparing participants for building trusting, respectful, and professionally constructive relationships in social settings. Preliminary observations indicated the presence of barriers in the awareness of specific values among university administrators, teachers, and students belonging to different faculties. In particular, survey results showed that respondents lacked sufficient knowledge about other faculties and demonstrated an indifferent attitude, which they perceived as normal behavior.

Figure 1.

Final level of students' professional competence development

Therefore, special attention was given to designing socio-academic case studies. It was considered appropriate that university administrators engage in targeted and individualized communication with each student, using various information-exchange forms such as online interviews, video messages, and brochures. The socio-academic cases were based on real-life interpersonal situations and structured according to the concentric method — from simple to complex. Task difficulty levels were pre-determined, and participants who faced challenges in completing tasks were provided with supportive visual or audio materials. In cases where university administrators or teachers found certain tasks difficult, supplementary questions recalling previously studied material were applied. The essence of this method lies in solving new problems based on previously accumulated experience. When presenting the socio-academic cases designed via the concentric method, integration of real-life events and situations was also ensured.

Discussion. In order to verify the reliability, accuracy, and validity of the obtained results, statistical analysis was conducted. The statistical analysis was carried out using mathematical–statistical methods based on the Chi-square (χ^2) criterion. The following statistical formulas and functions were used in the process. The application of the χ^2 method in the research requires testing the hypothesis that the general population — that is, the educational process — follows a normal distribution law. To compare the academic performance indicators obtained in the experimental and control groups, the average values of the performance scores in the groups were taken as and respectively. Here, x_i and y_i represent the academic performance indicators of students in the experimental and control groups, taking values of 5, 4, and 3. m_j refers to the frequency of repeated scores, and N denotes the number of students involved in the experiment in each group.

The development of students' professional competence on the basis of pedagogical facilitation was studied through an in-depth analysis of the pedagogical practice in higher educational institutions. As a result, the main factors influencing the development of professional competence among students were identified, and new methods and pedagogical approaches aimed at meeting their socio-psychological and educational needs were implemented. These practices contributed to strengthening social communication and collaboration among students, fostering their personal and professional growth, and increasing the effectiveness of the educational process.

As a result, the effectiveness of developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation improved significantly:

- by 1.15 times (15%) according to the axiological criterion,

- by 1.14 times (14%) according to the gnoseological criterion,
- by 1.14 times (14%) according to the praxeological criterion.

These improvements were statistically verified and confirmed using mathematical–statistical techniques.

Conclusion

1. The rapid socio-economic changes occurring in modern society impose new and complex demands on the education system. Meeting these requirements necessitates the modernization of higher pedagogical education, which in turn requires the introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches aimed at developing students' general and professional competencies. Accordingly, this dissertation provides a comprehensive theoretical and practical analysis of the processes of developing students' professional competence based on pedagogical facilitation.

2. The conceptual foundations of pedagogical facilitation and its theoretical aspects as a necessary pedagogical approach were examined in the research. The significance of pedagogical facilitation in fostering students' professional competence, as well as systematic approaches to its implementation in educational practice, were widely discussed. This provided opportunities to create conditions that support learners' individual abilities, interests, and professional development.

3. The pedagogical conditions and specific mechanisms required for developing students' professional competence were identified. The role of pedagogical facilitation in enhancing teachers' professional competencies, as well as the contribution of interdisciplinary integration to student learning, was comprehensively explored. Pedagogical facilitation established a strong pedagogical foundation for the effective development of students' professional competencies.

4. The effectiveness of using various forms of educational activities — such as classroom and extracurricular sessions, competitions, conferences, olympiads, micro-teaching, discussions, video lessons, business games, and diverse teaching strategies — was empirically validated in student practice.

5. The content and results of the experimental work aimed at developing students' professional competence through pedagogical facilitation demonstrated its positive impact on the educational process. The findings confirmed the effectiveness of pedagogical facilitation in fostering students' professional competence.

6. The analyses conducted as part of the study showed that pedagogical facilitation plays a significant role in developing students' professional competence. This approach effectively stimulates learners' personal and professional growth, enhances their collaboration skills, and supports the development of personal and professional competencies essential for successful professional practice.

7. Throughout the research, the implementation of pedagogical facilitation in higher education was scientifically substantiated, and its importance in improving educational quality was demonstrated. The practical application of pedagogical facilitation opened new opportunities for developing students' professional competence, thereby contributing to the overall effectiveness of the educational process.

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